

Thermionic Emission and Catalytic Activity. Part II. Thoria-Ceria Surfaces. A Contribution to the Theory of Welsbach Gas Mantle.

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Various theories have been put forward to account for the increase in the light emissivity of the gas mantle containing 99.1% thoria and 0.9% ceria. Lewis (*Chem. News*, 1905, 91, 62) gives a complete summary of the work done so far on the subject. Westphal, suggested that the emissivity is due to the combination of an acidic oxide like thoria with that of a basic one like ceria. But Bunte (*cf.* Lewis, *loc. cit.*) put forward the idea that the mantle surface is catalytically active and the chemical reaction of the burning gases on the surface heats up the refractory material to such high temperatures that the glow occurs. In order to produce light emissivity of such magnitude as in the gas mantle, Rubens (*Ann. physik*, 1906, iv, 20, 593) has shown that a black body temperature of at least 1600° is required. However, Le Chatelier and Boudouard (*Compt. rend.*, 1898, 126, 1861) found that thoria-ceria mixtures exhibited unequal emissivity for different regions in the visible part of the spectrum and that these mixtures conformed more to a coloured body radiator. Nernst and Bose (*Physikal. Z.*, 1900, 1, 289) also found that these mixtures gave rise to selective radiation when heated in a Bunsen flame. Bunte later abandoned his catalysis theory and preferred the radiation theory on the basis of the results of his co-workers, Schmidt and others who showed that the light emissivity of the mantle was the same as that of the mixture even though heated to the same temperature in a muffle furnace. The experimental method of these authors has been objected to by Lewis (*loc. cit.*).

On the other hand White and Travers (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1902, 21, 1012) maintains that the temperature of heating has no correlation with light emissivity. A thoria surface heated up to 1510° gave only 1.2 C. P. per cu. ft. of gas, while a mantle surface at 1404° gave 15.7 C. P. per cu. ft. They consider that a solid solution of ceria in thoria occurs, which exhibits a maximum efficiency in converting

heat into light. That a solid solution of ceria in thoria occurs is confirmed well by the experiments of Meyer and Anschutz (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2639). M. Chas. Ferry (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1902, vii, 27, 433) thinks that ceria is finely divided and dispersed as a solid solution in thoria and helps to increase the catalytic activity of thoria by condensing the gases on the surface and that the chemical reaction gives rise to the high temperature and luminosity.

Recently Swan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 780) has shown that the maximum catalytic efficiency of ceria-thoria mixtures towards electrolytic gas mixtures is also found to occur with a surface containing 0.8% of ceria. He concluded that ceria acts as an oxygen-carrying promoter to the catalyst material thoria (*cf.* Wyruboff and V. B. Lewis, Taylor, "Catalysis in Theory and Practice," 1926, p. 199) or increases the electron emission of thoria, which causes greater ionisation of the reacting gases. He leaves the question open between these two possibilities. Even if the first alternative is taken in preference to the latter, there is no reason why a mixture containing only 1% of ceria should show maximum catalytic activity and luminosity.

In Part I of this series (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 5, 685) the author has drawn attention to the complete analogy that exists between thermionic emission and catalysis and has further shown that the interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen on the surfaces of platinum and thoriated tungsten was perceptible at the same temperature at which thermionic emission was also evident. It appears interesting to connect the two sets of observations by attributing thermionic emission as the primary cause of chemical reaction at the surfaces of incandescent bodies.

The example of the Welsbach gas mantle forms an interesting study in this connection. It is the object of this paper to study in a comparative way the emission of electricity from a platinum wire coated with mixtures of ceria and thoria of different amounts and see if the maximum thermionic emission from these surfaces occurs also at the same proportion of thoria and ceria (99:1), which is known to give maximum light emissivity and catalytic efficiency.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus and the experimental methods are exactly the same as in the previous part (*loc. cit.*), except that the spiral MacLeod

gauge was replaced by the more common form. A complete discussion of the limitations of the experimental methods are to be found there. The heating current in this case is supplied by a 10 volt battery through a rheostat. In measuring thermionic currents a micro-ammeter was used for the platinum wire and a sensitive galvanometer of the D'Arsonval type was used for the wires coated with thoria-ceria mixtures. In order to minimise the table leak, all the pieces of the measuring instruments were set on ebonite sheets. The table was heavily waxed with paraffin. The key switch in the galvanometer circuit was put on by means of a long ebonite rod.

Coating of the wires.—Weighed quantities of the nitrates of thorium and cerium, which would give the required proportion of thoria-ceria on ignition, were dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and mixed. The platinum wire was dipped in the syrupy solution and was heated outside by a small current to dull red glow, when the nitrates decomposed leaving a thin coating of the mixed oxides. This process was repeated carefully twice or thrice till a uniform and an adherent coating was obtained.

Temperature measurement.—The temperature of the hot wire was calculated from a knowledge of its resistance. The resistance of the wire at the melting point of ice and steam was measured with a Robertson bridge with compensating leads joined to 1 cm. of platinum wire in the circuit. This allows sufficiently for the cooling effect at the leads while the wire is heated. The resistances of the wire at the higher temperatures were calculated by noting the heating current in the circuit and the voltage across the ends of the wire. A sensitive ammeter and a voltmeter were employed. The temperature coefficient of resistance of the platinum wire was 38.4×10^{-4} . For the coated wires the temperature coefficient was assumed to be the same as that of platinum, since thoria and ceria are poor conductors of heat. The resistances of the wire calculated from these data could be taken with confidence and an error of even 0.01 ohm in the neighbourhood of 1000° makes only a difference of less than 5° in the calculated temperature. Hence the temperature measurements are quite reliable.

FIG. 1.

Pt. wire. $\log T = 3.1235$. $T = 1329^\circ$.

FIG. 2.

Thoria:ceria : : 98.83 : 1.17. $\log T = 2.9996$ $T = 999.5^\circ$.

FIG. 3.

Thoria : ceria : : 99.12 : 0.88. $\log T = 2.9990$. $T = 909.6^\circ$.

FIG. 4.

Thoria : ceria : : 98.97 : 1.03. $\log T = 2.9770$. $T = 948^\circ$.

Figs. 1-4 present the summary of the results on thermionic emission from platinum and platinum coated with thoria-ceria mixtures of varying composition. As in the previous work the temperatures at which thermionic emission is just perceptible or commences was found for each of these surfaces. The logarithms of the temperatures of the glowing wires were plotted against the galvanometer deflection. Duplicates agree well as seen from the graphs. These graphs are straight lines at low temperatures and when produced cut the X-axis sharply at the same point. But at higher temperatures they suddenly bend and go up. This is due to large currents being set up owing to ionisation due to collision with the gases evolved in the tube during the course of the experiment. Quantitative measurement of electron emission at any one temperature for each of these surfaces was not made but a comparison of the temperatures at which the emission was perceptible for these surfaces was made. That surface which at any temperature would exhibit maximum emissivity over the others would give rise to incipient emission at a far lower temperature than that of the others. Table I gives the temperatures (to the nearest degree) obtained from the graphs at which thermionic emission is just perceptible over various thoria-ceria surfaces.

TABLE I.

Surface.	Temperature at which thermionic emission is just perceptible.				
Platinum	1329°
Thoria-ceria	98.83 :	1.17	1000°
Do	98.97 :	1.03	948°
Do	99.12 :	0.88	1000°

It is seen from the results that the temperature at which thermionic emission is perceptible is minimum with a thoria-ceria surface containing 98.97% of thoria and 1.03% ceria. Consequently this surface should give rise to maximum electron emission in comparison with others. This result when considered with those of the light emissivity of the gas mantle and that of the catalytic activity of thoria-ceria (*loc. cit.*) provides an interesting basis for the explanation of activation of gases at catalytic surfaces and in particular the light emissivity of incandescent mantles. On the basis of the results obtained here and in the previous part (*loc. cit.*), it could be definitely stated that the activation of gases on the surfaces of catalysts depends on the capacity of the surface to emit electrons. The light emissivity of the gas mantle is a consequence of the oxidation of kerosene hydrocarbons on the surface of the mantle which is also dependent on the electron emission. A further discussion on the theoretical bearing of the catalytic activation of gases on the electron emission of the catalyst will form the subject of another communication.

SUMMARY.

1. A review of the various theories put forward to explain the brilliance of the Welsbach gas mantle is made.

2. Comparative measurements of thermionic emission from the surfaces of platinum, and thoria-ceria mixture of varying percentages, are made.

3. A mixture of thoria-ceria containing 1% of ceria is found to give rise to incipient electron emission at a lower temperature than those containing more or less amounts of ceria than 1%; this is identified to give the maximum electron emission than the other mixtures at the same temperature.

4. Catalytic activation of gases, of which the example of the Welsbach gas mantle is a particular case, is definitely attributed to electron emission from that catalyst surface.

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